

THE ROLE OF THE METHODOLOGICAL COMPONENT IN THE STRUCTURE OF THE TRAINING COURSE FOR GUIDES AND GUIDE-INTERPRETERS

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Annotation: The article considers various models of training aimed at developing professional competencies of guide-interpreters, analyzes traditional and innovative methods, as well as the role of information technologies in the educational process. Attention is paid to the use of authentic materials, blended learning, project activities, and interactive teaching methods. Expected results include increasing the efficiency of training specialists through the integration of theoretical knowledge and practical skills in real professional conditions.

Key words: Modern methods, translation theory, guide-interpreter skills, educational process, technologies.

Modern approaches to training guides and interpreters. Blended learning is an approach that combines traditional teaching methods and the use of online resources. This approach allows students to not only study theoretical materials, but also take online courses, watch authentic videos and participate in virtual excursions. Blended learning can significantly improve the level of students' training, as it allows them to study materials at a convenient time and review complex topics. This is especially important in conditions where standard lectures may not provide a sufficient level of practical knowledge. Authentic materials in training. The use of authentic materials, such as video recordings of real excursions, interviews with tourists, travel reports and other International Conference on Linguistics, Literature And Translation resources, allows students to get acquainted with a real situation that arises during an excursion. This contributes to the development of intercultural competence, and also helps students better understand what problems may arise in real excursion practice. Authentic materials promote the active development of listening and understanding skills in a foreign language, which is critical for the work of a guide-interpreter.

Project-based learning is actively used in a number of educational institutions and involves students completing real tasks, such as preparing and conducting a tour, creating translated texts and presentations. This approach allows students to develop practical skills and effectively prepare for work in real tours and excursions. Project-based learning also helps develop leadership skills, the ability to work in a team and organize events, which is an integral part of the work of a guide-interpreter. The role of information technology in training. Modern information technologies significantly affect the training process of guide-interpreters.

The use of virtual reality and augmented reality allows you to create realistic educational situations that reproduce real tourist routes. This helps students better prepare for their future professional activities. Virtual tours, simulators and interactive learning resources allow students to feel like a guide and go through allstages of a tour. These methods are becoming important tools for developing the necessary skills and self-confidence in students. International experience in training guide-interpreters shows that training in different countries is based on different approaches, depending on the national specificities of tourism. For example, in Europe, models oriented towards multicultural training are widely used, which allows students to better understand various cultural contexts and the peculiarities of tourists'

perception of historical and cultural sites. In Asia, virtual reality technologies are actively used, which allows students to immerse themselves in a cultural environment without having to travel abroad. These innovations open up new opportunities for improving the quality of education and adapting students to a globalized world. Models of training guide-interpreters continue to evolve in response to the requirements of the modern tourism industry. It is important that educational programs combine traditional methods with innovations such as blended learning, the use of authentic materials and information technology. These approaches will help students develop not only language skills but also the practical competencies necessary for successful work in the tourism sector.

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